

How Do Different Machine Learning Approaches to Short-Term Human Trajectory Prediction Compare in Terms of Accuracy and Prediction Speed on a Custom-Collected Dataset of Walking Humans?

Clemens Herzig, Marius Führer
University of Applied Sciences Technikum Wien
Vienna, Austria

{cleherzig@gmail.com, marius.fuehrer@technikum-wien.at}

Abstract—Human trajectory prediction is an important component of safety-critical systems such as collaborative robotics and autonomous vehicles. Accurate forecasting of future human motion can improve decision-making and reduce the risk of accidents in environments where humans and automated systems interact. Despite substantial progress in machine learning-based trajectory prediction, practical deployment remains challenging due to trade-offs between predictive accuracy, computational efficiency, and robustness.

This study presents a comparative evaluation of classical statistical methods and machine learning approaches for short-term one-shot human trajectory prediction using a custom-collected dataset of walking humans. A dataset containing 208 trajectory sequences from 16 participants was recorded using an RGB-D camera and annotated using pose estimation and tracking methods. Five prediction approaches were evaluated: Constant Velocity (CV), Kalman Filter (KF), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU), and Transformer models.

The models were assessed under varying observation and prediction horizons using Average Displacement Error (ADE), Final Displacement Error (FDE), and inference time. Results show that learning-based approaches consistently outperform classical methods in prediction accuracy, while classical approaches provide superior computational efficiency and runtime stability. Among the evaluated methods, the LSTM achieved the most balanced trade-off between accuracy and efficiency, whereas the Transformer achieved the highest overall predictive performance at increased computational cost. The findings highlight the importance of selecting trajectory prediction models according to application-specific constraints, particularly in real-time environments where both predictive quality and computational efficiency are critical.

Index Terms—Human trajectory prediction, machine learning, deep learning, LSTM, Transformer, Kalman filter, real-time systems, human motion forecasting

I. INTRODUCTION

The ability to predict future human movement is essential for a wide range of intelligent systems, including autonomous vehicles, service robots, industrial automation platforms, and collaborative robotic environments. Reliable prediction of future trajectories allows automated systems to anticipate human behavior and react proactively, thereby improving safety and operational efficiency [1].

Human trajectory prediction has evolved from geometric and tracking-based approaches toward data-driven machine learning methods capable of modeling complex temporal dependencies and nonlinear motion patterns [2]. Recent research has demonstrated the effectiveness of recurrent neural networks, attention mechanisms, contextual reasoning, and pose-based representations for improving prediction performance [3], [4], [5].

Although prediction accuracy has improved substantially, practical deployment remains challenging. Many existing studies focus primarily on maximizing predictive performance while paying comparatively little attention to computational efficiency and real-time usability. This limitation is particularly relevant in applications with strict latency requirements.

Furthermore, many trajectory prediction approaches rely on autoregressive forecasting, where future positions are generated iteratively. While effective, such approaches may introduce cumulative error and increased computational overhead. One-shot prediction approaches offer an attractive alternative by generating complete future trajectories in a single forward pass.

This work investigates the trade-off between prediction accuracy and computational efficiency through a systematic comparison of classical statistical approaches and machine learning models using a custom-collected dataset of walking humans. The study addresses the following research questions:

- How do different trajectory prediction approaches compare in terms of accuracy and computational efficiency?
- How does observation horizon length affect prediction performance?
- How does prediction horizon length influence forecasting accuracy?
- What differences exist between learning-based and classical statistical approaches?

II. METHODS

A. Dataset

A custom dataset was collected using an Intel RealSense D456 RGB-D camera operating at 30 FPS with a resolution

of 640×480 pixels. The dataset contains 208 trajectory sequences obtained from 16 participants exhibiting diverse physical characteristics and walking behaviors.

Individual sequences ranged from approximately 8 to 25 seconds in duration. Participants were instructed to walk naturally in a public environment with minimal restrictions, producing realistic trajectory variations and environmental noise.

B. Annotation Pipeline

Human pose annotations were generated using the YOLOv11 pose estimation model combined with ByteTrack-based temporal tracking [6], [7]. Frame-wise annotations included body keypoints, bounding boxes, and tracking identifiers.

The walking trajectory of each participant was approximated using the midpoint between the left and right ankle keypoints. Median depth values extracted from RGB-D measurements were added as additional spatial features.

C. Preprocessing

Preprocessing was intentionally kept minimal to preserve real-world sensor noise. Missing detections and incomplete depth measurements were interpolated using temporal linear interpolation. Apart from basic scaling and interpolation, no extensive smoothing or filtering procedures were applied.

D. Prediction Models

Five prediction approaches were evaluated:

- 1) Constant Velocity (CV)
- 2) Kalman Filter (KF) [8]
- 3) Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) [9]
- 4) Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) [10]
- 5) Transformer [11]

All approaches used identical trajectory representations to ensure fair comparison. Learning-based models were trained to predict future relative displacements, which were subsequently integrated to obtain complete trajectories.

E. Trajectory Representation and Training Objective

All learning-based models received a multivariate representation of human motion as input. For each frame, the complete human pose estimated by the pose detector was provided, preserving spatial information about body configuration and movement. In addition, the trajectory was represented using the center keypoint extracted from the detected pose, which served as the primary reference point for trajectory prediction.

To capture motion dynamics, velocity and acceleration features were computed from consecutive trajectory positions and included as additional input channels. This representation enabled the models to learn not only spatial location information but also temporal motion characteristics describing changes in movement over time.

The learning-based models were trained using a trajectory-based loss function. Predicted and ground-truth velocity sequences were converted into trajectories through cumulative

summation of the predicted displacements. The loss was then computed on the resulting trajectories, encouraging temporal consistency throughout the prediction horizon while penalizing both intermediate and final positional deviations.

Model parameters were optimized using backpropagation. Recurrent architectures (LSTM and GRU) were trained using Backpropagation Through Time (BPTT), while the Transformer model was optimized using standard backpropagation through its encoder architecture [12]. Validation was performed after each training epoch to monitor generalization performance on previously unseen trajectory sequences and to reduce the risk of overfitting.

F. Training Configuration

The dataset was divided into training (70%), validation (15%), and testing (15%) subsets.

Two observation horizons were evaluated:

- 15 frames (approximately 0.5 s)
- 30 frames (approximately 1.0 s)

Three prediction horizons were evaluated:

- 30 frames (approximately 1 s)
- 60 frames (approximately 2 s)
- 90 frames (approximately 3 s)

Learning-based models were trained using the Adam optimizer [13] with a learning rate of 10^{-3} , batch size 16, and 40 training epochs.

G. Evaluation Metrics

Performance was evaluated using:

- Average Displacement Error (ADE)
- Final Displacement Error (FDE)
- Inference time

Statistical significance was assessed using Friedman and ANOVA tests.

III. RESULTS

A. Overall Model Performance

Table I summarizes the overall performance of all evaluated approaches. The learning-based methods consistently outperformed the classical baselines in terms of trajectory prediction accuracy. The LSTM achieved the lowest average displacement error (ADE) and final displacement error (FDE), while the Transformer produced comparable results at the cost of higher computational requirements. The GRU improved substantially over the classical methods but remained less accurate than the LSTM and Transformer.

The Constant Velocity (CV) and Kalman Filter (KF) baselines exhibited significantly higher prediction errors but required less computational effort. These findings indicate that recurrent and attention-based neural networks can better capture temporal dependencies in human motion trajectories than traditional motion models.

TABLE I
OVERALL MODEL PERFORMANCE.

Model	Mean ADE	Mean FDE	Mean Time (s)
CV	21.539	44.117	0.204
KF	17.103	36.604	0.437
LSTM	11.129	22.070	0.562
GRU	12.485	24.077	0.436
Transformer	11.542	22.466	0.702

B. Effect of Observation Horizon

Figure 1 illustrates the influence of observation horizon length on prediction accuracy. Increasing the amount of observed trajectory history generally improved the performance of the LSTM and Transformer models. These architectures benefited from additional temporal context, allowing them to better infer future pedestrian motion patterns.

The GRU showed a different behavior. While moderate observation horizons improved prediction quality, longer histories often resulted in reduced accuracy. This suggests that the GRU was less capable of exploiting long-term temporal dependencies than the LSTM. The classical methods exhibited only minor sensitivity to observation horizon length because their predictions relied primarily on recent motion estimates.

Fig. 1. ADE and FDE for different observation horizons.

C. Effect of Prediction Horizon

Figure 2 shows the relationship between prediction horizon length and forecasting accuracy. As expected, all methods experienced increasing errors when predicting further into the future. This trend reflects the growing uncertainty associated with long-term human motion prediction.

The LSTM and Transformer consistently maintained the lowest ADE and FDE values across all tested prediction horizons. Although their performance degraded with increasing prediction distance, the rate of degradation remained lower than that observed for the GRU, KF, and CV approaches.

Fig. 2. ADE and FDE for different prediction horizons.

D. Computational Efficiency

To analyze the computational efficiency of the evaluated models in more detail, runtime was separated into two perspectives: the influence of the observation horizon and the influence of the prediction horizon.

Figure 3 illustrates the computational cost with respect to different observation horizon lengths. As expected, classical methods such as Constant Velocity (CV) and the Kalman Filter (KF) exhibit consistently low and stable inference times, since their computational complexity scales minimally with input sequence length. In contrast, learning-based models show increased runtime as the observation horizon grows, due to the higher amount of sequential input data processed by the neural architectures.

Among the neural models, the Transformer consistently requires the highest computational cost across all observation horizons. The LSTM and GRU demonstrate similar runtime increase behavior, with the GRU being more efficient in all configurations rivaling the Kalman Filter in speed.

Figure 4 shows the effect of increasing prediction horizon length on computational efficiency. While classical approaches remain largely unaffected, learning-based models show a mild increase in inference time as longer output sequences are generated. This effect is most pronounced for the Transformer due to its attention-based decoding mechanism.

Overall, the Constant Velocity model remains the most computationally efficient approach, followed closely by the Kalman Filter and the GRU Model. Among the learning-based methods, the LSTM provides the best trade-off between

Fig. 3. Computational efficiency with respect to observation horizon length.

computational cost and predictive performance, while the Transformer consistently incurs the highest runtime.

Fig. 4. Computational efficiency with respect to prediction horizon length.

IV. DISCUSSION

The results demonstrate that learning-based trajectory prediction models substantially outperform classical motion models when predicting short-term pedestrian trajectories. The LSTM achieved the best overall performance, producing the lowest ADE and FDE values while maintaining moderate computational requirements.

Although the Transformer achieved competitive accuracy, its higher computational cost limited its practical advantages in the investigated setting. The relatively small dataset may

also have restricted the Transformer’s ability to fully exploit its representational capacity. Transformers typically benefit from significantly larger training datasets than recurrent architectures.

The GRU provided an interesting intermediate solution. While computationally efficient, its prediction quality deteriorated more rapidly as observation horizons increased. This finding suggests that the GRU struggled to retain long-term temporal information compared with the LSTM’s dedicated memory-cell architecture.

The experiments further confirmed that increasing the observation horizon can generally improve prediction accuracy, particularly for models capable of learning long-term dependencies. Conversely, increasing the prediction horizon consistently reduced accuracy across all approaches due to the inherent uncertainty of future pedestrian behavior.

From an application perspective, the results indicate that LSTM-based predictors currently provide the most practical solution for short-term human trajectory prediction in autonomous navigation systems. They combine high prediction accuracy with moderate computational requirements, making them suitable for deployment in real-time environments.

V. CONCLUSION

This study presented a comparative evaluation of classical statistical and machine learning approaches for short-term one-shot human trajectory prediction using a custom-collected dataset of walking humans.

Learning-based models consistently achieved superior prediction accuracy, while classical approaches provided greater computational efficiency and runtime stability. Observation horizon length influenced models differently depending on architecture, whereas increasing prediction horizon length reduced accuracy across all methods.

Among the evaluated approaches, the LSTM offered the most favorable balance between predictive performance and computational efficiency. The Transformer achieved highly competitive predictive performance but required substantially greater computational resources.

These findings demonstrate that no single trajectory prediction model is universally optimal. Instead, model selection should be guided by application-specific requirements, particularly with respect to latency constraints, computational resources, and prediction accuracy requirements.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Clemens Herzig conducted the research as part of the master’s thesis, including study conception, data collection, analysis, and drafting of the manuscript. The full master’s thesis is available from the library of the UAS Technikum Wien.

Marius Führer supervised the research process on a regular basis, provided conceptual guidance, critically reviewed the manuscript, and approved the final version for publication.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The dataset and implementation materials are available upon reasonable request from the authors, subject to applicable ethical, privacy, and institutional restrictions.

Fig. 5. Representative prediction examples from evaluated models.

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